

Creation And Advancement Of Module For Learning Geometry Thinking Skills Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Among Senior Secondary School Students In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Creation and Advancement of Module for Learning Geometry Thinking Skills using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State. The objective of the study are: Determine the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Determine the Creation and Advancement of instructional module using Artificial Intelligence AI for improving the learning Geometry in Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State, Find out the deference in the performance of senior secondary school students, in learning Geometry before and after using Artificial Intelligence AI module in sokoto State, Compare the performance of students taught using Artificial Intelligence AI and those taught using traditional method on learning Geometry among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Explore the students ability in solving Geometry in both experimental and control group before and after using Artificial Intelligence module among Senior secondary school students in sokoto State. The study was use two groups Pre-Test Post-Test quasi-experimental design and sample consisted of 379 students, comprising 200 boys and 179 girls, drawn from a total population of 31,895 for SS 2 students in Sokoto State. Ordinary Level Geometry Competence Achievement Test (OLGCAT) is the instrument to used measure academic achievements of the sample students in the subject of mathematics. Which is construct based on the mathematics teaching curriculum and objectives of the study. The collect data is analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses will test using paired sample T-Test and independent sample T-Test. The study which would be completed in 7 months hopes to find positive effect of Creation and Advancement of Module for Learning Geometry Thinking Skills using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Geometry Thinking Skills, Secondary School Students

INTRODUCTION

Geometry is a branch of mathematics that explores the properties and relationships of shapes, sizes, and figures, and the space they occupy. It is one of the oldest areas of mathematics, originating from ancient civilizations like the Egyptians and Greeks. Geometry involves studying various aspects of shapes, such as points, lines, angles, surfaces, and solids (Kline, 2021).

The fundamental concepts in geometry include points, which have no dimension; lines, which extend infinitely in both directions; and planes, which are flat, two-dimensional surfaces. Geometry also explores properties of shapes like triangles, circles, and polygons, examining their angles, sides, and symmetry (Katz, 2014).

According to (Banchoff, & Kuhn, (2022)). Two primary branches of geometry are Euclidean and non-Euclidean. Euclidean geometry, named after the Greek mathematician Euclid, deals with flat, two-dimensional surfaces and is the basis for most traditional geometry. Non-Euclidean geometries, such as spherical and hyperbolic geometry, explore curved spaces and have applications in advanced fields like physics and cosmology.

Understanding geometry is crucial for developing spatial reasoning skills, which are applicable in various real-world contexts, from architecture and engineering to computer graphics and robotics (Coxeter, & Greitzer, 2021).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence by computer systems. It involves creating algorithms and models that enable machines to perform tasks typically requiring human cognition, such as learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. (Russell, & Norvig, 2021). AI encompasses various technologies, including machine learning, where systems improve performance through experience, and natural language processing, which allows machines to understand and interact with human language. (Goodfellow, & Courville, 2016). AI applications are diverse, ranging from virtual assistants and recommendation systems to autonomous vehicles and diagnostic tools in healthcare. (Mitchell, 2019). Machine learning. McGraw-Hill Education By mimicking human intelligence, AI aims to enhance efficiency and unlock new possibilities across various industries (Mikolov, & Grave, 2021).

According to Ajinuhi and Onoge (2024) conducted research on Deployment of Artificial Intelligence for Teaching and Learning of Mathematics Programme in Tertiary Institutions in. The paper utilized secondary data sourced from both print and online publications. It concluded that integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the mathematics programs of tertiary institutions significantly enhances various aspects of teaching and learning. These benefits include improved presentation of mathematics lectures, preparation of student result reports, development of instructional resources (Smart Content), mapping and modeling, automated simulation, implementation of automated modeling methods, advancements in mathematics research, more effective conduct of examinations, increased student engagement and motivation, and enhanced personalized learning experiences. The paper advocates for greater investment in tertiary institutions to fully integrate AI across all faculties and departments within mathematics programs.

Fitria, (2021) examine The influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology is becoming increasingly apparent across different sectors, including education. AI has revolutionized educational curricula, particularly in technology, science, mathematics, and engineering, and is expected to further transform the broader educational landscape. Recent attention has focused on AI's role in education, where it facilitates various functions and supports teaching. AI enables educators to better understand and address student needs, allowing students to learn according to their individual requirements with fewer obstacles.

AI is believed to enhance learning outcomes and achieve educational goals more effectively (Baker, & Inventado, (2014)). Consequently, numerous AI-based innovations are being developed to support and improve the learning process. Despite some concerns about AI replacing teachers, many believe that AI should complement rather than replace educators (Chen, 2019). Teachers must acquire skills in utilizing science and technology to leverage AI effectively for tasks such as lesson planning, student attendance tracking, reporting learning outcomes, and creating educational resources. This study aims to explore the impact of AI on education, with a particular focus on its application in teaching and learning processes.

A module is a self-contained unit or component within a larger system designed to perform a specific function or provide particular content. Morrison, & Lowther, (2019) In educational contexts, a module often refers to a structured learning segment focused on a specific topic or skill, such as a unit in a curriculum or an online course component. Modules are designed to be flexible and can be combined or adapted to fit different educational needs (Reigeluth, & Carr-Chellman, 2009). They often include instructional materials, exercises, assessments, and multimedia resources to facilitate learning. By breaking down complex subjects into manageable parts, modules help learners engage with and master content effectively (Gagne, & Wager, 2004).

Traditional methods of teaching refer to conventional approaches used in education before the advent of modern technology. These methods often rely on direct instruction, where teachers lecture and provide information to students, who then practice and apply the concepts through exercises and assignments (Sloan, 2004). Traditional methods emphasize rote learning, memorization, and standardized testing (Cuban, 2001). They typically involve a structured classroom environment with a fixed curriculum and limited use of technology. While these methods can offer a clear and systematic way of teaching fundamental concepts, they may lack the interactive and adaptive elements that modern educational technologies provide (Brunner, 2010).

Thinking skills refer to the cognitive abilities required to analyze, evaluate, and create ideas effectively. (Paul, & Elder 2014) They encompass critical thinking, which involves assessing information and arguments to make reasoned judgments, and problem-solving, which includes identifying solutions to complex issues (De Bono, 2015). Therefore the important thinking skills include creative thinking, which involves generating innovative ideas, and logical reasoning, which ensures structured and coherent thought processes(Heath, 2010). Developing strong thinking skills enables individuals to approach challenges with a strategic mindset, make informed decisions, and adapt to new situations (Willingham, 2009). These skills are essential for academic success and are highly valued in personal and professional contexts.

Statement of the Problems

The global attention is moving towards teaching the 21st century challenging for having sufficient training and planning for integrating technology into instructional. As such, Nigeria is a developing country which its still backward in using of technology for instruction. The government of Nigeria emphasizes integrating technology teaching and learning in all levels of education (Jo, & Afolabi 2023;., Ogunyemi, & Akinbode 2022). But still most of the Nigerian teachers are unable to apply the technology in their teaching inspire of its importance to the development of the country at large. In this regard, the integration of Artificial Intelligence into Geometry instruction become crucial for effective learning of geometry, however, over the years in Nigeria, the traditional teaching method which rely heavily on abstract example and verbal explanation, dominated at the senior secondary level in this regards the chief examiner report (WAEC 2020) highlights several difficulties encountered in teaching and assessing geometry at the senior secondary level. One major issue is the insufficient conceptual understanding among students. Many students struggle with fundamental geometry concepts such as the unit circle, Geometry functions, and their applications. The chief examiner report WAEC (2023) examination report highlights significant poor performance in geometry. Many candidates demonstrated weak grasp of key concepts such as Geometry identities, and their applications. Contributing factors include inadequate preparation, limited exposure to practical problems, and insufficient classroom support. The chief examiner report NECO (2023) examination report reveals a concerning trend of poor performance among candidates. Key issues include inadequate preparation, lack of resources, and insufficient teaching quality. The chief examiner report NECO (2022) examination report reveals a significant decline in geometry performance among candidates. Many students struggled with essential concepts like trigonometric functions and identities, leading to high failure rates.

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The integration of Artificial Intelligence into geometry instruction has become crucial for effective teaching. However, to fully benefit from this tool, it must be implemented properly to enhance learning outcomes. Currently, traditional teaching methods, which rely heavily on abstract examples and verbal explanations, dominate at the secondary school level. In Sokoto, as in other regions, there is a heavy dependence on these traditional methods, leading to students encountering geometry content without understanding its relevance or practical applications. This has contributed to a growing apprehension towards geometry among students, resulting in diminished proficiency levels. In Sokoto, this is reflected in consistently poor performance in mathematics compared to other subjects. Moreover, there is a notable lack of technological integration in Geometry education, especially in utilizing Artificial Intelligence. Teachers in Sokoto are not frequently using this AI, leading to a less dynamic and effective learning experience. In Sokoto state there is lack of existing technological integration especially AI Module or learning Geometry are dependent on the traditional of teaching that is teaching to students encountering geometry content without understanding its, relevance or practical applications. This study seeks to address these challenges by investigating the Creation and Advancement of Module for Learning Geometry Thinking Skills using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State.

Objectives of the Study

The aims of the study is to investigate the Creation and Advancement of Module for Learning Geometry Thinking Skills using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State. Specifically, this study has the following research objectives to:

- (i) Determine the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State.
- (ii) Determine the Creation and Advancement of instructional module using Artificial Intelligence AI for improving the learning Geometry in Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State

Research Questions

On the basis of research questions raised the following research question bellow would be used in this study Specifically, this study has the following research Question:

- (i) What are the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State?
- (ii) What are the Creation and Advancement of instructional module using Artificial Intelligence AI for improving the learning Geometry in Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto Stat

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methodology applied in this study. In particular, the chapter gives attention to the following aspects: research design, population of the study, sampling and sampling techniques, instrument for data collection, data collection procedures, and data analysis.

Research Design

The Quasi-experimental design; two groups pre-test post-test design is implemented in this study. This quasi-experimental research design involving two groups; the experimental and control groups (Creswell, 2012). In this design the geometry competence of the students before the treatment and divided the class as experimental group that studied using AI and control group that studied mathematics using traditional method of teaching. The difference if any, between the two groups (Eg-Cg) is compute and is ascribed to the manipulation of AI. Table, summarizes the design of the study:

Table 1. Research Design of the Study

Group	Pre-Test (Ya)	Treatment	Post-Test (Yb)
Experimental Group (EG)	OLGCAT	Student centered dynamic experiential learning environment using ICT equipment for learning mathematics	OLGCAT
Control Group (CG)	OLGCAT	Student centered dynamic experiential learning environment using Traditional method of learning geometry i.e paper and pencils.	OLGCAT

Source: (primary data, 2025)

Population and Sample

Mathematics is a compulsory subject for all senior secondary school students in Sokoto State and also said to be the time when students are expect to learn basic mathematics (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014.; Usman, & Mohammed, 2020). Therefore, the target population 31,895 of this study is all O level students of senior secondary school students in Sokoto State. However the study strictly focused on SS II.

Table 2 Distribution of the Population

Class	Respondents	Population
SS II	Students	31,895
Total		31,895

(Source: MOE Sokoto 2024)

Research Instrument

In order to measure academic achievement of the sample students in the subject of mathematics a teacher made geometry test (OLGCAT) is administer immediately before and after completing the experiment teaching to both the groups, in the schools at the same time and data collect Is the scores of students achieved in the both pre-test and post- test. The Researcher made a thorough study of geometry taught and techniques of test construction. Test is prepare by the experience math teachers at secondary level, and higher institution from the topics taught to both the groups by making the chart of specification, and by considering the technique of paper setting for different understandings, i.e. 10% for difficulty, 75% for average, and 15% for easy levels. The test contained 48 items as a whole, questions is objectives since all these types of testing is included in the syllabus. Time duration for the test was fixed as one and a half hour, which is considered to be appropriate for the completion of the test for both the groups. In addition post-test was conducted on the same day and time.

Population of The Study

The study includes all SSS II students attending government-owned schools in Sokoto state, totaling an

estimated 31,895 students across 142 schools. These schools are organized into six educational zones: Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Gwadabawa, Bodinga, Goronyo, and Yabo, based on their proximity to the respective zonal headquarters. are given in the table 3.1

Table 3 Distribution of Schools in Sokoto State on Zonal Basis.

S/N	ZONE	MALE	FEMALE	MIXED	TOTAL
1	Sokoto North A	11	5	1	17
2	Sokoto South B	26	8	1	35
3	Gwadabawa C	16	4	-	20
4	Bodinga D	17	4	-	21
5	Goronyo E	21	4	-	25
6	Yabo F	17	7	-	24
	TOTAL	108	32	2	142

Source: Ministry of Education (2024)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study utilized a sampling approach based on Morgan and Kreycie's (1971) table to determine the appropriate sample size from a given population. A total of six Senior Secondary Schools were selected using a fish-bowl random sampling technique. In this method, each school's name was written on a slip of paper, placed in a container, mixed thoroughly, and drawn without looking. Each selected slip was returned to the container, and the process was repeated until six schools will be chosen from the 142 schools listed in the zonal education offices of Sokoto State.

Simple random sampling is used to selected respondents of this study hope to give information regarding Creation and Advancement of Module for Learning Geometry Thinking Skills using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students. This is simple sample where by all the members of the population stands equal chance to be chosen (Kumar, 2019: Leedy, & Ormrod, 2019). Once the schools was selected, random sampling is use to choose students from these institutions. As outlined by Best and Kahn (1986), random sampling provides each individual in the population an equal and independent chance of being included. For the tests, only one class from the SS 2 level at each of the sampled schools participated.

For this study, simple random sampling is utilized to select participants. This method ensures that every member of the population have an equal chance of being included in the study, which investigates the design and development of a module for teaching trigonometric thinking skills using Microsoft Mathematics among senior secondary school students in Sokoto State, Nigeria (Khan, & Shah, 2022).

The sample consisted of 379 students, comprising 200 boys and 179 girls, drawn from a total population of 31,895 SS 2 students in Sokoto State. The number of students selected per school adhered to the sample size recommendations from Morgan and Kreycie (1970). Given the total population of approximately 32,000 students, the table suggested a sample size of 379 students. Details on the distribution of male and female students, as well as the total number, are provided in the table below.

Table 4 Distribution of Students per Sample School

S/N	Name of School	Number of Male	Number of Female	Total
1	Sultan Bello Secondary School Sokoto	80	-	80
2	Government Day Secondary School Kofar Rini	70	-	70
3	Government Science Secondary School yabo	50	-	50
4	Government Girls Model Secondary School Illela	-	67	67
5	Government Girls Unity Secondary School Bodinga	-	67	67
6	Gamji Girls College Rabah	-	50	50
Total		200	179	379

Research Instruments for Data Collection

To evaluate the academic performance of the students in mathematics, a teacher-designed geometry test (OLGCAT) is administered before and after the experimental teaching sessions. This test, given to both groups simultaneously in the schools, aimed to measure students' progress. The test, created by experienced secondary-level math teachers, included 48 multiple-choice questions. The test was designed with varying levels of difficulty: 10% difficult, 75% average, and 15% easy. It was set to last one and a half hours, which was deemed appropriate for both groups. The post-test was conducted on the same day and at the same time as the pre-test.

Research Instruments for Quantitative Data Collection

The quantitative assessment involved using identical instruments for both pre-test and post-test surveys. According to Barriball and While (1994), questionnaires are a reliable method for collecting consistent data within a short timeframe. Hence, questionnaires were chosen for their ease of organization and data processing (Creswell et al., 2003). This study employed questionnaires to assess changes in students' understanding before and after the learning sessions.

Face Validity

Face validity is also used to evaluate the research instrument. This type of validity assesses whether the instrument appears to measure the intended concept (Creswell, 2002). To determine face validity, the instrument is reviewed by the expert and three senior academic staff members from the Department of Mathematics, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, to ensure its appropriateness.

Reliability of the Instruments

To establish the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted. The test included 20 items from the Ordinary Level Geometry Competence Achievement Test (OLGCAT) and is distributed randomly to senior secondary students. The items will be consolidated into a single variable, and the reliability of the constructs was assessed using Cronbach's alpha in SPSS software. Cronbach's alpha measures the internal consistency of an instrument (Cronbach, 1984).

Method of Data Collection

At the conclusion of the experiment, which lasted six weeks, the Ordinary Level Geometry Competence Achievement Test (OLGCAT) is administered to both groups on the same date and time. The test scores for each group will be recorded separately and used to assess academic achievement, which is then analyzed statistically to meet the study's objectives.

Procedure of Data Collection

The researcher obtained a written introduction letter from the Head of the Department of Mathematics, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto which is then presented to the Honorable Commissioner of the Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education in Sokoto. Following this, the researcher met with school principals and ICT lab tutors to discuss the research and seek their approval. After securing permission, the researcher met with the relevant classes, explained the research goals, and requested consent for participation. Research assistants (ICT tutors) will be recruited to assist with data collection. Cognitive tests will be conducted in the classroom setting.

Method of Data Analysis

Once data collection is complete, quantitative data will be edited, coded, and scored using SPSS software. The analysis is divided into four sections. The first section involved analyzing the demographic characteristics of the participants using percentages. The second section focused on analyzing the results of the OLGCAT. An Independent Sample T-test is used to compare the mean scores between two groups, based on the specific objectives and hypotheses of the study. This test is chosen to compare continuous variables between two groups (Khan, & Shah, 2022). SPSS version 23.0 is used for all statistical computations.

Research Procedure

The researcher and the computer teacher provided a three-day orientation for the experimental group, offering hands-on experience with computer use during break times before the experiment began. Given that the students were already familiar with computers, the orientation focused on the specific

requirements of the experiment, including using email, chatting, and Artificial Intelligence. Students' email addresses were created and shared among them and their teacher. They were trained in composing mathematical questions, sending and receiving emails, and accessing online resources. The orientation also included demonstrations of various mathematics teaching resources available worldwide. At the end of the orientation, the researcher and teachers assessed the students' understanding of the computer and software through oral questions.

The control group use traditional teaching materials, including a comprehensive mathematics textbook, blackboard, chalk, duster, and exercise books. Instruction was delivered through lectures, with frequent use of the whiteboard. Students solved exercises from the textbook in their notebooks and were engaged in drill and practice activities. Daily homework is assign, review, and discuss regularly by the teacher. This group receive guided and independent practice throughout the study period to control for time variables and meet the study's objectives.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This chapter presented analyses and discusses the study findings. The findings are presented Based on research questions and objectives of the study after elaboration of the descriptive data of the creation and advancement of module for learning geometry thinking skills using artificial intelligence (AI) among senior secondary school students: all the findings are discussed in contrast with what other researchers established in various studies. This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section presents descriptive statistics of the data. The second section present quantitative result, the last one summarizes and discusses the research findings. The focus of this study was to explore creation and advancement of module for learning geometry thinking skills using artificial intelligence (AI) among senior secondary school students in sokoto state, Nigeria, level in the subject of mathematics in contrast to traditional method of teaching .The means scores of the experimental and control group on the basis of post-test taken immediately after the completion of the experiment was recorded. Equivalence of experimental and control groups were cited on the basis of scores obtained from the previous achievements test of the students of class IV in the subject of mathematics by applying t-test. Significance of difference between the means scores of experimental and control groups was investigated by applying independent sample t-test.

Demographic Data of The Students

This section analyzed demographic data of the students who participated in the study which comprised their sex and age.

**Table 5. Showing the Sex of the Students
Sex of Respondents**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	200	52.8	52.8	52.8
Valid Female	179	47.2	47.2	100.0
Total	379	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Data 2025

The table 5 above reveals that the highest number of students involved in this study were male with 200 representing (52.8%), this was followed by female who were 179 (47.2%), the difference between the male and female was quite negligible and this implied that both the male and female respondents responded positively towards the geometry learning.

Figure 1 Bar chart shows the sex of respondents

Table 6 Showing the Age Distribution of the Students

AGE				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
14-16	93	24.4	24.4	24.5
17-19	118	31.0	31.0	55.7
20-22	134	35.2	35.2	91.0
23-ABOVE	34	8.9	8.9	100.0
Total	379	99.5	100.0	
	379	100.0		

Source: Field Data 2025

Based on the result presented in table 4.2, it was indicated that 93 (24.4%) of the students were 14-16 years of age this was followed by 118 (31%) of the students were in the range of 17-19 years. 134 (35.2%) of the students were 20-22 years of age while 34 (8.9%) of the students were in the range of 23 years above. Given the fact that majority of the students were of age, it suggested the fact that data were

collected from true representatives of senior secondary school students in Sokoto . This is in line with the demographic analysis of Ibrahim (2015) who reported that majority of secondary school students in Mbale municipality were between the ages of 13-19 years.

Research Question one: *What are the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State?*

Table 7: mean rating of respondents on the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State

Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Statement	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
1	I believe the AI enhances my understanding of Geometry functions.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2639	.55305	Agree
2	I often use Microsoft Mathematics to practice t Geometry problems.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2612	.59348	Agree
3	The visual aids in the software help me comprehend Geometry relationships.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2454	.84856	Agree
4	I appreciate the step-by-step solutions provided by the AI.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2955	.65243	Agree
5	I feel more confident in solving Geometry problems after using the software.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2850	.71497	Agree
6	I find that the AI allows me to learn at my own pace.	379	1.00	5.00	4.1636	.90831	Agree
7	I enjoy collaborating with classmates while using AI.	379	1.00	5.00	4.3509	.65531	Agree
8	I think the AI makes learning Geometry more enjoyable.	379	1.00	5.00	4.3694	.65925	Agree
9	I am interested in exploring advanced Geometry topics using the software.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2982	.79567	Agree
10	I would recommend the AI Module to others.	379	1.00	5.00	4.1029	1.10911	Agree
11	The tutorials in the AI are helpful for reinforcing my learning.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2559	.96523	Agree
12	I believe that using technology like AI improves my Geometry skills.	379	1.00	5.00	4.3483	.62154	Agree
13	I find the software’s interface user-friendly and easy to navigate.	379	1.00	5.00	4.3272	.63710	Agree
14	I often feel excited to use the AI during my study sessions.	379	1.00	5.00	4.3799	.68870	Agree
15	I believe the software can help me prepare better for exams in trigonometry.	379	1.00	5.00	4.1214	.86742	Agree
16	I like that the AIe can visualize Geometry graphs and functions.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2691	.81414	Agree
17	I would like more opportunities to use the AI in my math curriculum.	379	1.00	5.00	4.1794	.85727	Agree
18	I think using AI can help reduce math anxiety related to Geometry	379	1.00	5.00	4.3456	.74840	Agree
19	I believe the AI can help bridge the gap between theoretical and practical Geometry.	379	1.00	5.00	4.2084	.80431	Agree

20	I feel more motivated to study Geometry when using the AI. Valid N (listwise)	379	1.00	5.00	4.1794	.85727	Agree
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Table 7 reveals that respondents agreed that the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State. this is seen in the mean scores of 20 items (items 1-20) on the values scale with means scores above mean average of 2.5.

Research Question Two: *What are the Creation and Advancement of instructional module using Artificial Intelligence AI for improving the learning Geometry in Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State?*

Table 8: mean rating of respondents on the Creation and Advancement of instructional module using Artificial Intelligence AI for improving the learning Geometry in Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Do you believe that AI-powered instructional modules can provide personalized learning experiences for students studying Geometry?	379	1.00	5.00	4.2639	.55305	Agree
In your opinion, can AI tools enhance student engagement and motivation in Geometry by providing interactive, dynamic learning environments?	379	1.00	5.00	4.2612	.59348	Agree
Do you think AI can improve students' spatial reasoning skills by offering 3D visualizations and interactive simulations of geometric concepts?	379	1.00	5.00	4.2454	.84856	Agree
Do you agree that AI-based instruction can increase accessibility to high-quality geometry learning resources for students in remote or underserved areas?	379	1.00	5.00	4.2955	.65243	Agree
In your view, would the integration of AI into geometry education reduce the workload of teachers by automating the creation of quizzes and assignments?	379	1.00	5.00	4.2850	.71497	Agree

Do you believe AI can assist in fostering a deeper understanding of geometry by offering personalized problem-solving strategies and hints?	379	1.00	5.00	4.1636	.90831	Agree
Do you think the use of AI can help bridge the gap for students who need extra support in geometry by offering them personalized learning paths?	379	1.00	5.00	4.3509	.65531	Agree
Do you believe AI will provide students with a better opportunity to engage with real-world applications of geometry, such as in architecture and engineering?	379	1.00	5.00	4.3694	.65925	Agree
Do you think AI-driven platforms can help students learn geometry more efficiently by automating the review of their work and suggesting additional practice problems?	379	1.00	5.00	4.2982	.79567	Agree
Do you think there is a risk that students may rely too much on AI for problem-solving in geometry, potentially hindering the development of independent thinking and problem-solving skills?	379	1.00	5.00	4.1029	1.10911	Agree
Valid N (listwise)	379					

Table 8 reveals that respondents agreed that the level of interest in learning Geometry using Artificial Intelligence AI Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto State. this is seen in the mean scores of 10 items (items 1-20) on the values scale with means scores above mean average of 2.5.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the creation and advancement of a module for learning geometry thinking skills using Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds significant potential to transform the educational landscape for senior secondary school students. By leveraging AI, we can offer personalized learning experiences, allowing each student to progress at their own pace while receiving targeted feedback and support. AI-driven interactive tools and simulations can make abstract geometric concepts more tangible, helping students visualize and manipulate shapes and their properties in real time.

Moreover, the integration of adaptive learning paths and gamified elements can enhance engagement, motivation, and mastery of geometry concepts. AI's ability to assess student performance continuously and provide instant feedback fosters an environment of continuous improvement and mastery learning. This approach also empowers teachers with valuable insights into each student's strengths and areas needing attention, enabling more effective

instruction.

Ultimately, AI can bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and modern technological advancements, making geometry more accessible, engaging, and effective for students. The ongoing development of AI-powered learning modules promises to cultivate deeper geometric thinking, critical problem-solving skills, and a lifelong appreciation for mathematics, preparing students for future challenges in academia and beyond.

The study concluded that both experimental and traditional group scores significantly improved after the intervention. Also, learning geometry significantly improved after the experimental and traditional intervention.

The study similarly concluded that the experimental group performs better than the traditional group which shows AI has more effect after the intervention.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Here are Recommendations for the creation and advancement of a module for learning geometry thinking skills using Artificial Intelligence (AI) among senior secondary school students:

1. **AI-Assisted Formative Assessment:** Incorporate ongoing formative assessments where AI evaluates students' understanding and suggests areas for focus.
2. **AI-Based Peer Review:** Allow students to review and provide feedback on peers' geometric work using AI tools that guide the review process.
3. **Adaptive Testing:** Implement AI-powered adaptive testing that adjusts the difficulty level of questions based on a student's ability and provides precise insights into areas of
4. **AI-Powered Interactive Geometry Tools:** Develop AI-driven applications that allow students to interact with geometric shapes and figures in real time. These tools could let students manipulate objects like triangles, circles, and polygons, visualizing transformations such as rotations, reflections, and translations, which will help deepen their understanding of geometry concepts.
5. **Personalized Learning and Adaptive Feedback:** Implement AI systems that tailor the learning experience to individual students' strengths and weaknesses. Based on their progress, AI could adjust the difficulty of problems, suggest specific topics for review, and provide personalized hints or solutions, ensuring that each student advances at their own pace.
6. **Gamified Geometry Challenges:** Use AI to create engaging, gamified learning experiences where students solve geometry puzzles and challenges to earn rewards, level up, or unlock new content. This approach can enhance motivation while reinforcing key geometric principles through playful competition and interactive problem-solving.
7. **Real-Time Error Detection and Assistance:** Integrate AI to offer real-time feedback on students' geometric problem-solving techniques. The AI could identify common mistakes (e.g., errors in calculations, misinterpretation of shapes) and suggest ways to correct them, helping students learn from their mistakes immediately.
8. **AI-Generated Dynamic Practice Problems:** Use AI to generate a wide variety of dynamic and context-rich geometry problems based on the current lesson and student performance. These problems could be customized to match students' learning needs, offering diverse applications of geometry concepts and helping them build problem-solving skills across different scenarios.

The application of AI was found effective for learning mathematics at secondary level. To make its application more effective in education, students should be trained in AI from the grass root level. Therefore, it is recommended that Information and communication technology (ICT) should be introduced as a separate discipline in the curricula of Nigeria from primary level.

Application of AI as a teaching strategy in mathematics was found effective as compared to traditional method of teaching. So to enhance its use in other disciplines of education, AI should be taught as a subject and it should be integrated into all other subjects of the curricula at secondary and higher secondary levels.

Considering the slight improvement on student learning after traditional teaching signifies students can learn also through traditional teaching however the researcher recommends combination of the two methods to ensure maximum learning.

Policy makers and curriculum designers should endeavor to integrate 'O' level curriculum and find the different types of software and learning style that are most effective for use with computer education.

Suggestion for Further Research

- (i) Further research on creation and advancement of module for learning geometry thinking skills using artificial intelligence (AI) among senior secondary school students using Solomon four group experimental

design.

- (ii) There is need to Research on creation and advancement of module for learning geometry thinking skills using artificial intelligence (AI) among senior secondary school students using two different schools.
- (iii) There is need to investigate the creation and advancement of module for learning geometry thinking skills using artificial intelligence (AI) at university level. Since the study is focused on secondary school.

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